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6th ANNUAL REPORT
for the period ending June 30, 1962

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES INC.

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21

6th ANNUAL REPORT

for the period ending June 30, 1962

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 1025 Connecticut Avenue, N.W. Washington 6, D. C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

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* Dr. Butterfield served as a member of the Executive Committee through November 28, 1961. He has been succeeded by Dr. Hard.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

Late in 1960 the Ford Foundation approved a new grant of eight million dollars to enable the Council to continue for an additional seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems, and at the same time further to concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized scientific personnel.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

The Council on Library Resources

THE SIXTH YEAR

The methods employed by libraries from earliest times for organizing their collections have been basically inventorial in character. But for some time it has been increasingly clear to some observers that these methods are inadequate to the purpose intended — that of making the collections useful.

“Even the modern great library,” said Dr. Vannevar Bush in 1945, “is not generally consulted; it is nibbled at by a few.” The reason for this, he suggested, was that “The summation of human experience is being expanded at a prodigious rate, and the means we use for threading our way through the consequent maze to the momentarily important item is the same as was used in the days of square-rigged ships.” But, he added, “The world has arrived at an age of cheap complex devices of great reliability; and something is bound to come of it”; and he suggested a number of applications of such devices to what has since come to be known as the “information problem.”¹

From these and similar observations has come the quest for the “push-button library,” and much effort and intelligence has been devoted to it. Progress has been slow but has taken place, and there are numerous operating systems in which “push-button” machine selection has replaced manual selection; e.g., with respect to libraries of engineering drawings, or of reports of chemical research. Even for the more traditional methods of library work, automata have speeded up the making of indexes and concordances. Meanwhile, copious research is under way looking to the development of devices for reading printed text; for converting oral to graphic systems of communication and vice versa, for indexing, abstracting and inter-lingual translation; for spatial compression of records; and for improved methods of classification and indexing.

Few of these developments have as yet affected any but clerical operations in general libraries. For one thing, except for certain special applications such as those just mentioned,

¹ Vannevar Bush: *As We May Think*. *Atlantic Monthly* 176: 101-108. July 1945.

LIBRARY 21 — *Above:* Overall view of American Library Association exhibit at the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle. The left circle includes the Automated Library Center, Ready Reference Center and Adult Reading Area. The right circle includes the Learning and Resources Center, Xerox Theater, Radio Corporation of America and National Cash Register exhibits, and stairway leading to the Children's World below. The circles are framed by a reflecting pool.

Below: Secretary of State Dean Rusk, center, examines answers to a choice of questions printed out by an information storage and retrieval system featured by a solid-state computer.

the service provided by the new mechanisms cannot yet compete either in cost or convenience with the traditional methods; for the purposes which most libraries serve, the book still provides the least expensive and most convenient form of storage of information, and the card catalog and the book-index the most flexible and effective instruments for reaching it. For another, even were techniques and devices developed which would enable a mechanized service to rival or even to exceed the satisfactoriness of traditional methods, the new mechanisms would require an expensive conversion of records to machine-readable form — typically microtext, punched cards or computer tape. It may be foreseen that records will eventually be initially published in such forms (and indeed, there are harbingers of this); but, meanwhile, libraries will necessarily be slow to convert.

The Council's program includes support of a number of projects of research and development looking to the application of the "advanced data processing" mechanisms to library work. As a result of one of these, a device has been constructed which stores microimages at a density rate of a million per cubic foot and locates any desired image and provides a re-enlargement ("hard copy") of it in less than a second. This is an outstanding engineering achievement, yet although the device will undoubtedly find special applications for which its speed and compression of storage commend it, it is for many applications inferior technologically as well as economically to its equivalent in books. In other projects the Council has supported general surveys of the possibilities of mechanization of university and other research libraries, an investigation of machine indexing, and an inquiry into the possibilities of machine searching of statutory law.

During the past year occasion offered opportunity for a public demonstration of elements of the progress toward the "pushbutton" library. The American Library Association was invited to participate in the Century 21 Exposition at Seattle, Washington, April - October 1962, with an exhibit having emphasis on the "library of the future." This presented an opportunity not only for demonstrating the traditional patterns of excellent library service, but also for showing some of the realities behind the talk of "push-button libraries." Accordingly, a grant by the Council to the Association made possible the necessary planning; and cooperation was secured from

industry and others to the extent that the resultant exhibit represented a total investment of more than \$2 million.

Reactions to the exhibit were interesting and informing. The traditionalists, as was expected, resented the intrusion of machines into a library exhibit as the negation of librarianship. The mechanists, on the other hand, felt the results of an investment of even this size to be trivial. The visiting public, estimated at over half a million, seemed in general to be more interested in microfilm reading machines (devices long established in research libraries) than in the robots. These reactions all suggest that the road to the "push-button" library will be long, slow and expensive, and that the book is in no foreseeable danger of displacement. Efforts to improve the book-based techniques of library work are, in this view, wholly justified.

Concepts and Problems of Libraries of the Future. In making a new grant to the Council for a period commencing with the year just past, the Trustees of the Ford Foundation made provision for the Council to "concentrate its work in the field of technical storage and retrieval of information through the creation of a laboratory or center involving the activities of specialized personnel." A careful survey was made of the possibilities. These included the equipping and staffing by the Council of a laboratory of its own, the development of a new facility in cooperation with some research institution, or an arrangement with an organization already possessing basic facilities in equipment and staff.

Similarly, there were a number of alternative possibilities for the program of such a center. Should it, assuming the persistence of certain patterns and conditions of library work, concentrate on the development of particular devices of great promise as viewed against the persisting framework? Or, at the other extreme, should it abandon all such assumptions and engage instead in a fundamental study of the processes of cognition which might suggest a totally new set of patterns and conditions? In exploring these questions the Council sought advice from a number of persons who have thought deeply on this subject.²

² Members of the Committee on the Laboratory are listed on page 5. Among others to whom the Council is most indebted in this exploration are Dr. William O. Baker, Dr. Lloyd V. Berkner, Dr. Richard H. Bolt, Dr. Caryl P. Haskins, Dr. Edwin H. Land, Dr. Anthony G. Oettinger, Dr. Emanuel R. Piore, Dr. Earl P. Stevenson and Dr. Warren Weaver.

In the event, the Council contracted, late in 1961, with the firm of Bolt Beranek and Newman, Inc., of Cambridge, Massachusetts, for exploratory "research on concepts and problems of libraries of the future," to be directed, in consultation with an advisory committee, by Dr. J. C. R. Licklider, formerly associate professor of psychology and communication at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, and active in research in the processing, communication and display of information. The contemplated research neither assumes the persistence of present patterns of library work, nor does it commence with the cognitive process. Rather, it assumes merely that information must be stored and organized, that devices will be required for this purpose, and that human beings must interact with these devices, and that improvements can be effected in all these areas.

The first year's work accordingly proposed to develop the agenda for further research through a number of preliminary inquiries, including the preparation of a quantitative, functional description of libraries as they now operate; formulation of a statement of the functions that should be fulfilled by library systems; the examination of related sciences and technologies for their potential support of library operations; an analysis of aims, methods and problems in information storage and retrieval and in memory organization; and the performance of research on specific problems of man-machine communication and "artificial intelligence." It is proposed to publish the results of these studies as completed.

Summary of Activity in 1962. Forty grants, contracts and other allocations, representing a somewhat larger number of projects (for example, a number of separate projects were provided for under the allocation to the Library Technology Project) were made by the Council during 1962. These totalled \$961,128. Twenty-five of the allocations were for new projects; thirteen were for extensions or renewals of prior undertakings.

The following pages describe, in the categorization which has proved useful in previous reports, the projects assisted during the year as well as the results of projects completed.

VERNER W. CLAPP
President

Improvement of the Means of Bibliographic Access

(Included here are all the means by which the existence of a source of recorded information becomes known and from which is learned the location at which it may be consulted or whence a copy may be obtained.)

International Conference on Cataloging Principles. Paris 1961. Two events shortly after the Council's establishment raised the hope that the coordination of cataloging practices among the nations of the world, long supposed to be irrevocably divided between two principal systems, might not be as impossible as believed. The first of these events was the meeting of the German Library Association in Lübeck in June 1957, at which the Council had made representation by the American Library Association possible, where it appeared that the adherents of the two systems were simultaneously moving toward a common middle ground.³ The second was the agreement by the proponents of American catalog code revision, reached in another meeting assisted by the Council, to defer to the initiative of the International Federation of Library Associations, which, under the leadership of Sir Frank Francis (subsequently appointed Director of the British Museum) had since 1954 been exploring the possibilities of such coordination.⁴

It was apparent that any major effort to produce international consensus in a field such as this would require very deliberate preparation. The planning was, accordingly, spread over three years. The culmination of the first stage was reached at a preliminary meeting, held in London in July 1959, involving representatives from 15 countries and preceded by the distribution of a number of working papers. At this meeting the agenda and arrangements were set for a later, fully international conference, and wide notice was given as to the intensity of its purpose. The preliminary meeting also defined the area within which agreement might be obtained, and identified the issues that would require resolution in order to obtain such agreement.⁵

³ I: 26-28. (Citations in this form are to the Council's annual reports; in the present instance to its *First Annual Report*, pages 26-28.)

⁴ II: 9-11.

⁵ IV: 23.

The second step ensued as projected. An international organizing committee was appointed consisting of Mr. A. H. Chaplin (British Museum) who also served as Executive Secretary, M. Paul Poindron (Bibliothèque Nationale, Paris), Dr. Ludwig Sickmann (Lehrinstitut des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen, Cologne), and Miss N. A. Lavrova (All-Union Book Chamber, Moscow). Arrangements were made to enable the members of the committee to attend the American Library Association's Institute on Catalog Code Revision at McGill University in the summer of 1960.⁶ Seventeen working papers were commissioned, translated and distributed. The International Conference on Cataloging Principles, involving 105 participants from 53 countries and 12 international organizations, in addition to 104 observers from 20 countries, met at the Unesco Conference Building October 9-18, 1961, under the chairmanship of Sir Frank Francis. A Statement of Principles, representing a very substantial measure of agreement, was adopted, and the Conference called on the participating countries to take action to carry these principles into their cataloging rules and the compilation of their national bibliographies. The preliminary report of the Conference has been given wide circulation⁷ and a formal report is in preparation for publication.

Although a year has not as yet elapsed since the conference, there are numerous indications that its recommendations are having effect.

National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections. Late in 1958 the Council made a grant to the Library of Congress to enable it to establish a National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, a finding medium long desired by scholars in the historical disciplines. The immediate goal was to bring together, in addition to some 3,000 collections in the Library of Congress itself, uniform descriptions of some 24,000 known collections in approximately 75 cooperating libraries, and to print and make available catalog cards for these collections, thus creating a union card catalog for these materials and simultaneously making it possible for any library to create a similar record. It was proposed that each card should bear, in addition to the

⁶ IV: 13.

⁷ International Federation of Library Associations: International Conference on Cataloging Principles: Preliminary Official Report. *Unesco Bulletin for Libraries* 16:53-63 (March-April 1962). Also in *Libri*: 12:61-76 (1962).

description of a collection, a listing of the important persons and subjects under which it might be indexed.

Work under the original grant, expected to be for two years, has been extended with the assistance of a small supplement made this past year to three and a half years. During that time the catalog has been firmly established. Offers of cooperation have been received from some 900 repositories, and reports of some 13,000 collections have already been received from approximately 500 of these. More than 10,000 collections have been cataloged on the basis of these reports and printed catalog cards have been issued.

In addition, it has been found possible to effect without expense to the grant what had initially been a hope but was not an undertaking: publication of a catalog in book form, which has come from the press since the conclusion of the fiscal year.⁸ Representing collections in some 400 repositories, 7,300 cards have been combined with indexes into the volume. The important information gathered by this project will thus be made widely accessible in convenient form and at small cost. This low cost has, of course, derived from the fact that much of the letterpress work had already been performed in the printing of the cards.

The Council has approved support of this project for an additional year.

Guide to Photocopied Historical Manuscripts. In 1957 the Council made a grant to the American Historical Association to aid in the preparation of a guide to photocopied historical materials.⁹ The work has been completed by Dr. Richard W. Hale, Jr., Archivist of The Commonwealth of Massachusetts, under the auspices of the association's Committee on Documentary Reproduction, and published.¹⁰

International Inventory of Musical Sources. The *Répertoire International des Sources Musicales*, a bibliography and finding list of manuscripts and printed works to 1800, is being com-

⁸ U. S. Library of Congress: *The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, 1959-1961, Based on Reports from American Repositories of Manuscripts.* Ann Arbor, Michigan: J. W. Edwards, Publisher, Inc., 1962. viii, 1061 p.

⁹ II: 19-20.

¹⁰ Richard W. Hale, Jr., editor. *Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials in the United States and Canada.* Ithaca, New York, Cornell University Press, Published for the American Historical Association, 1961. xxxiv, 241 p.

piled under the auspices of a Joint Commission sponsored by the International Musicological Society and the International Federation of Music Libraries. This effort, in which some 17 countries are participating, and which is expected to result in a series of some 30 volumes (of which the first has appeared) is one of the most important of current international bibliographical efforts, the more important because of the international character of music and because of the general lack of representation of music in the usual bibliographical sources.

In 1960 the Council assisted the Joint Commission in establishing editorial offices at Kassel (where the city government has contributed office space).¹¹ During the year past the Council made another, terminal, grant for the Commission's work.

Meanwhile, because of the wide scattering of the relevant musical sources in the United States and for want of a central gathering effort, the holdings of American libraries, though important as a whole, were not becoming represented, as they should, in the *Répertoire*. The Council consequently made a grant to enable the Music Library Association to assemble the record of these holdings and to edit them not only for inclusion in the *Répertoire*, but also for recording in the National Union Catalog. As of June 30, 1962, the Washington office had forwarded to Kassel more than 12,000 cards, representing holdings of more than 150 American libraries.

Feasibility of a Caribbean Bibliographic Center. The great difficulties of procurement of books from Latin American countries and the defects of the bibliographic mechanisms for recording the publications of these countries are interrelated problems. Over the past few years an informal cooperative group, the Seminar on the Acquisition of Latin American Library Materials, has contributed greatly to the development of methods for combating these obstacles. During the past year the Council made a small grant to the group to explore the feasibility of a bibliographic center for the Caribbean area and to prepare a plan for it. This study was undertaken by Miss Marietta Daniels of the Columbus Memorial Library of the Pan American Union and Mr. Robert E. Kingery of the New York Public Library.

¹¹ V: 19.

Book-Selection. College libraries, and many public libraries with similar book-selection problems, are faced with choosing from the many thousands of books published each year those which promise the greatest usefulness to their readers. This they must do with smaller budgets and much less opportunity for expert advice than are available to the great research libraries such as those of universities.

In the past a most useful book-selection tool for these libraries was Charles B. Shaw's *A List of Books for College Libraries*,¹² but this has been succeeded by the *Lamont Library Catalogue*,¹³ which in its turn has felt the touch of obsolescence, and no satisfactory means have been as yet developed for keeping such basic lists up to date.

The fact is, of course, that although such lists are of great use both as guides and as yardsticks in the formation of basic collections, an even more urgent need is felt by college libraries for a current book-selection service to provide prompt and scholarly evaluations — capable of carrying weight with teaching staffs — of those books which should be considered for inclusion in their collections. Such a current service would, besides, provide a means for revising a basic list from time to time.

A plan for such a current book-selection service has been in process of development for several years.¹⁴ The number of college libraries, which would be the market primarily addressed, is not large (approximately 2,000), while the cost of a current fortnightly or monthly service, carrying paid reviews, is high. However, a method of publication has been projected which promises success. Accordingly, the Council has made a grant to the American Library Association to launch the service on an experimental basis, with the intention of commencing publication in 1963.

Cooperative Book-Processing. Mrs. Brigitte L. Kenney's report, *Cooperative Centralized Processing*, published by the American Library Association in 1959, described the accom-

¹² [Prepared for the Carnegie Corporation of New York], 2d preliminary edition. Chicago: American Library Association, 1931. [Supplement], 1931-38. 1940.

¹³ Prepared by Philip J. McNiff. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1953.

¹⁴ III: 25-26; IV: 15.

plishments of the Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc., at the end of its first year's operation. A new survey, to reflect a longer period of development, was desirable and a grant last year made this possible.¹⁵ A report by Mrs. Frances D. Carhart of the Des Moines Public Library, has now been published.¹⁶ Has the center realized its objective of effecting economies in book-processing, providing improved technical services and releasing time for more efficient public service? Mrs. Carhart gives an unqualified affirmative, supported by figures and descriptions of the center's operations. She concludes that the center has "set a pattern, unique at the time of its inception, for one plan of organizing centralized technical processing, and has furnished a noteworthy instance of successful cooperation."

A Numerical Code for Identifying Current Trade Publications. The report of the study conducted by Mr. Gustave A. Harrer of Boston University and Mr. Alex Ladenson of the Chicago Public Library, which has been described in previous reports,¹⁷ was given availability in the form of journal publication during the last year.¹⁸

Bibliographical Control of the Microforms. Professor Wesley Simonton's report of the investigation of this problem¹⁹ was published during the past year.²⁰

The Use of Classified Book Collections. The usefulness of an open-access bookstack is dependent upon the systematic arrangement of the books on the shelves, effected through the application of a shelf-classification scheme. The price paid for this usefulness occurs first in the cost of maintenance and application of the classification scheme, and second in the reservation of vacant space on the shelves to accommodate new arrivals, and the shifting of books when the vacant space does not occur at the needed points. Because of these and

¹⁵ V: 18.

¹⁶ Frances Dukes Carhart: *Southwest Missouri Library Service, Inc.; a Study in Cooperative Centralized Technical Services.* Chicago: American Library Association, 1962. x, 78 p.

¹⁷ IV: 15; V: 30-31.

¹⁸ G. A. Harrer and Alex Ladenson: A Proposal for a National Code Number System for Current Publications. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 6:4-12 (Winter 1962).

¹⁹ IV: 15; V: 31.

²⁰ Wesley Simonton: The Bibliographical Control of Microforms. *Library Resources & Technical Services* 6:29-40 (Winter 1962).

other attendant costs, large libraries are under great pressure to abandon the systematic arrangement of their books, and with it open-access, with the advantages which it gives the reader.

In 1960 the Council made a grant to the Library of Congress to study the use of its classified collections.²¹ It was intended that this should be a pilot study leading to other investigations of the use of shelf-classification in libraries of various types and sizes. Two reports have been made.²²

Shelf-Classification for Legal Publications. In 1958 the Council made a small grant to the Library of Congress to enable it to explore with the American Association of Law Libraries a plan for developing that part of its shelf-classification for legal works (Class K) relating to Anglo-American law. The importance of this project was described in a previous report.²³ The need for a shelf-classification for law books has become acute in recent years with a proliferation of publications which has been due in large part to the increasing importance of administrative law. Several law classification schemes have been developed to fill the need, but none of these is applied by any central service, and a library wishing to make use of one of them is compelled to perform its own classification. In the interest of efficiency it is desirable that classification assignments for law books, similarly as for the literature of other subjects, be available in a central cataloging service such as Library of Congress catalog cards; but a condition precedent is the development of that Library's inchoate Class K.

Following a series of studies over several years, consensus on a plan for the development of an Anglo-American law classification was reached early in 1962. In order to speed its execution and the commencement of benefits to be derived from it, the Council has made another grant to the Library for a two-year project which, it is proposed, will result in the publication of the classification schedule and the beginning of publication of classification assignments for new publications

²¹ IV: 17.

²² Saul Herner: *A Pilot Study of the Use of the Stacks of the Library of Congress*. Washington, D. C.: Herner and Company, 1960. 55 p.
Henry J. Dubester: Stack Use of a Research Library. *ALA Bulletin* 53: 891-893, November 1961.

²³ III: 23-24.

on the printed catalog' cards. The Library has announced the appointment, as principal consultant on the project, of Mr. Miles O. Price, Law Librarian Emeritus of Columbia University.

Mechanization of Production of Subject-Heading Lists. In 1960 the Council made it possible for the American Association of Law Libraries to engage in the first phase of an experiment for simplifying the production of a list of subject-headings for cataloging legal materials.²⁴ This initial phase was completed during the year. A basic list of headings was assembled and prepared on cards. From these the copy for a checklist was produced by sequential camera.²⁵ Copies of the checklist have been distributed as a basis for a collaborative editing effort. When the returns are in, it is expected that the card file can be revised and the final list produced with little new composition; also, the cards can be preserved for producing later revised editions.

"Coordinate Indexing" of Legal Materials. The term "coordinate indexing" takes its name from the familiar process by which a point in space is determined by the intersection of lines or planes. In a system using "coordinate indexing" the desired item is found at the "intersection" of the separate words to which it has been indexed rather than by a complete phrase containing all the words. Thus a document on "diabetes in infants" would not be indexed to the entire phrase but to the separate principal words of the phrase and would be recovered by collating all the entries on infants against all those on diabetes. This method of indexing has become familiar in the "coding" employed on punched cards. It is in general more suitable to machine manipulation than is the "subject-heading" method of indexing conventionally employed in library catalogs and book-indexes; it is claimed, too, to permit greater "depth" and precision of indexing at lower cost than the conventional method.

Last year's report recorded the placing of two contracts to test the claims of "coordinate indexing" in the field of law.²⁶ One of these was for an actual index of a particular body of

²⁴ IV: 15.

²⁵ *Checklist of Library of Congress Subject Headings for Law Material.* [Washington: American Association of Law Libraries, Committee on Cataloging and Classification, 1962] 305 p.

²⁶ V: 16.

law; the other was for prototypes of equipment to exploit the index when made.

Work has progressed on the index. Meanwhile, in order to involve those who may make use of it in its development and subsequent testing, the Council has made a small grant to the American Association of Law Libraries to designate a committee for this purpose, of which Mr. Julius J. Marke of the New York University School of Law, and president of the Association, is chairman.

Meanwhile, too, the prototypes of the equipment have been completed. This equipment contemplates that for each term used in the index there will be a card in which are punched holes representing the documents indexed to that term. An "intersection" of terms is discovered by superimposition of the cards for those terms, whereupon the "intersections" are identified by light penetrating the holes possessed in common by the cards. The special equipment involved consists of a camera intended to reduce the cards to cheaply reproducible microfilm, and a viewer to superimpose the microfilms. Testing of the equipment awaits the completion of the index.

Improvement of Catalog Card Stock. Because of the severity of their use, the catalog cards used by large libraries have generally been required to be of all-rag stock, and until recently this was the principal specification promising the desirable durability and permanence. It is now known, however, that by itself this is insufficient. Accordingly the Council made it possible for the Library Technology Project to investigate this topic.²⁷ The Project commissioned a study from Mr. W. J. Barrow, and has published his findings.²⁸ In the course of his investigation he tested a number of available card stocks, both rag and chemical wood. He found, among other things, that some chemical wood cards are superior to some all-rag cards. In a series of recommendations he suggested specifications for a card stock for heavily used catalogs. These recommendations have resulted in the availability of acceptable cards at prices lower than it was previously thought necessary to pay.

Catalog Card Reproduction. The proposal by Professor William N. Locke, Director of Libraries of the Massachusetts

²⁷ IV: 17.

²⁸ W. J. Barrow: *Permanence and Durability of Library Catalog Cards*. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association [1961] vii, 39 p.

Institute of Technology to devise a mechanism for producing catalog cards was mentioned briefly in last year's report.²⁹ The proposed device would consist of two manually operated keyboards, feeding into an electronic memory. Upon completion of composition of a catalog card on either of the keyboards, including the correction of errors and the designation of the entries under which individual cards would be filed, the memory would drive an electric typewriter, producing separately typed cards under the different entries as designated. It was estimated that such a machine might save the time of three persons in the MIT library alone. During the past year the design for the machine has been completed under contract to MIT by the firm of Edgerton, Germeshausen & Grier.³⁰ Further steps are now under consideration.

Improvement of the Means of Physical Access

(By the "means of physical access" are meant the devices and arrangements by which a source of recorded information, once identified, is placed in the reader's hands; they include, for example, methods of procurement, storage, preservation, copying and transmission.)

The W. J. Barrow Laboratory. Mr. William J. Barrow, of Richmond, Virginia, has made significant contributions to the arts of document and book preservation. The results of his investigations toward the solution of the deterioration-of-paper problem, performed under grants by the Council to the Virginia State Library, have been described in previous reports.³¹ In order to make it possible for him to continue to work on the problems of book preservation in libraries the Council has contracted with him to establish a laboratory devoted exclusively to the Council's projects. In fine space provided to him by the Virginia State Historical Society Mr. Barrow has equipped a laboratory with temperature and humidity controls believed to be the finest anywhere for the testing of paper products.

²⁹ V: 17.

³⁰ Richard E. Dolbear: *A Programmed Printer for the High-Speed Production of Catalog Card Sets*. Boston: Edgerton, Germeshausen & Grier, Inc. 1962. 68 p.

³¹ III: 32-33; IV: 27-29.

(It has increasingly appeared that temperature and especially humidity is critical in such testing.) The laboratory's work has begun with three assignments. One of these seeks the development of a deacidifying aerosol spray for delaying the deterioration of books. A second involves the investigation of adhesives for use in so-called "perfect" (or "adhesive") binding for library books, requiring the development of tests for predicting the longevity of such adhesives. The third is the study mentioned below.

Performance Standards for Library Binding. A grant to the American Library Association in 1960 made possible a survey of library requirements for bookbinding and the design of a further study to develop performance standards for this important library requirement which involves the expenditure of millions of dollars a year.³² A report was published.³³ During the present year a new grant enabled the Association to implement the recommendations of the report with an investigation leading to the development of standards and specifications. The Association, after exploring the various facilities for such a study, has assigned the task to the W. J. Barrow Laboratory.

A National Plan for the Preservation of Deteriorating Materials. The preliminary work on this topic by the Association of Research Libraries through a committee headed by Mr. Douglas W. Bryant of the Harvard University Library was mentioned in last year's report, as was the assistance given to these studies by the Council.³⁴ It was felt that certain preliminary facts need to be known: how great is the quantity of research materials in the libraries of the country, and what is their status with respect to deterioration (i.e., how many must be treated before 1970 if they are to be preserved, how many before 1980, etc.)? To provide some indications of the size of the problem a sampling study was designed by Mr. Randolph W. Church, State Librarian of Virginia, and executed for the Association by Triangle Research Associates, statistical consultants. The sample was based on the record of bookholdings of American libraries as represented by the National

³² V: 20.

³³ *Development of Performance Standards for Library Binding, Phase I; Report of the Survey Team.* Chicago: American Library Association, Library Technology Project, 1961.

³⁴ V: 21.

Union Catalog. The study indicates that there are 15.3 million cards in this catalog representing approximately 12.5 million titles. Of these, 10.5 million are separate book titles, comprising just short of three billion pages. Fifty-seven per cent of the total are estimated to have been printed since 1870, the date which marks the general adoption of wood pulp paper. The sampling also provides estimates of the number of books printed in each decade since that date as well as a distribution by country of origin. From these figures some further sampling and testing can provide an estimate of the expectancy of deterioration in the decades to come. The next steps in the matter are being explored.

ALA Joint Committee on a Permanent/Durable Book Paper. In September 1960 a meeting of paper makers, publishers, book manufacturers and librarians was held in Washington to discuss the results of Mr. Barrow's published study which suggested specifications for a permanent/durable book paper for library use and methods for manufacturing such a paper within the competitive price range of commercial book papers.³⁵ This group invited the American Library Association to establish a representative group for the continuing discussion of the subject and for search for acceptable solutions to the various problems. During the past year the Council enabled the Association to establish such a committee. After an initial meeting of the whole group, a subcommittee, of which Dr. Harry F. Lewis, Dean Emeritus of the Institute of Paper Chemistry, Appleton, Wisconsin, is chairman, has undertaken the tasks of weighing general acceptance of the Barrow specifications and of ascertaining whether additional research is needed.

Improved Archival Containers. Cardboard boxes have in recent years gained increasingly wide acceptance for the storage of manuscript materials in archives and libraries and are used in large quantities in the preservation of irreplaceable materials of frequently high historic importance. But the stock of which these boxes is constructed is chosen with too little regard to the characteristics needed to meet the special purposes which they serve: e.g., permanence and durability, freedom from potential threat of damage to their contents through migration

³⁵ V: 20.

of moisture or acidic residues, and ability to repel insects or to resist molds, moisture and fire.

Mr. Leon deValinger, Jr., the State Archivist of Delaware, who has the responsibility for testing all writing materials used for public records in the State, has proposed an inquiry looking to the development and testing of an improved cardboard for this purpose. A grant to make such research possible under the co-sponsorship of the State Archives of Delaware and the American Library Association is being administered by the Library Technology Project, working with an advisory committee of which Mr. deValinger is chairman, and a preliminary investigation has been commissioned from the Institute of Paper Chemistry.

Use of Microfilm. The Council has continued its search, previously reported at some length,³⁶ for devices to increase the contribution of microforms to individual research by freeing their use from dependence upon institutionalized non-portable viewing devices. The John R. Miles Company has continued the attempt to develop a suitable hand-reader based upon a variable 10x - 30x magnifier-microscope which was commenced last year.³⁷ The Battelle Memorial Institute completed its investigation of the factors affecting reader satisfaction in the viewing of microimages with a view to the development of more satisfactory devices, and reports have been published.³⁸ In this investigation a number of interesting discoveries were made, among which were that the viewing of a projected microimage can be more pleasing than the viewing of its original under suitable conditions of illumination, resolution and contrast. Based on the findings a series of recommendations are made. The Institute also fabricated two working models of viewers for individual use embodying new concepts — a shoulder-supported projection viewer and a virtual image viewer. These are now under study.

³⁶ IV: 31-37.

³⁷ V: 25.

³⁸ O. A. Ullrich, J. R. Stock, J. M. Dugan, L. E. Walkup: *Summary Report on Design Improvements for Simple Microimage Viewers*. Columbus, Ohio: Battelle Memorial Institute, 1961. 66 p.
L. E. Walkup, O. A. Ullrich, J. R. Stock, J. M. Dugan: The Design of Improved Microimage Readers for Promoting the Utilization of Microimages. In National Microfilm Association: *Proceedings* 11:283-310 (1962).

High-Density Storage of Micro-Images. For a century it has been possible to record documents at high ratios of reduction (100x or more), but this capability has found only occasional applications, such as in espionage. For library work the attractiveness of such high ratios of reduction consists not so much in the space-saving which results (though this might be important) but rather in the still more important possibility of inexpensive dissemination. For, at 100x reduction, 10,000 images can be confined in the area initially required by one, and it should therefore be possible to reproduce all 10,000 at a cost approximating that of one. An enormous library might thus be duplicated and disseminated at comparatively small cost.

To develop this possibility, in December 1958 the Council contracted with the Avco Manufacturing Company for the construction of the working model of a high-density photostore. The result of this project was described in an earlier report.³⁹ The device was capable of storing a million images at 140x reduction in a cubic foot and of finding any desired image in from 0.2 to 0.3 seconds. It could read the image out to a television screen, or transfer it to a memory tube so that it could be held for an extended period on the screen while the photostore was conducting other searches; or it could provide a microfilm copy of the image. No provision was made at that stage, however, for "hard copy" read-out — i.e., for the reproduction of the image in its original size.

A subsequent contract has provided for the development of an electrostatic "hard copy" output, and the work on this was completed during the past year, resulting in the construction of a prototype and the preparation of a report.⁴⁰

The principal components of the new read-out system are a 1½ inch vidicon (television camera) tube with its associated electronics, and an electrostatic printing tube with its associated paper-handling equipment. The desired image is found

³⁹ IV: 29-30. See also K. Bowker, L. H. Martin, E. J. Lucas, C. Phaneuf: *Technical Investigation of Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Final Report No. EW-6680.* Boston: Electronics Research Laboratories, Crosley Division, Avco Corporation, 1960. vi, 110 p.

⁴⁰ R. L. Waring: *Technical Investigations of Addition of a Hardcopy Output to the Elements of a Mechanized Library System, Final Report 940101.* Cincinnati, Ohio: Electronics and Ordnance Division, Avco Corporation, 1961. 43 p.

ELECTRONICS AND ORDNANCE DIVISION
Cincinnati 19, Ohio

VEBAC 102

This copy of an original typewritten page has been reproduced by a feasibility model of Elements of a Mechanized Library System designed and constructed under an agreement between the Council on Library Resources, Incorporated and the Avco Corporation. The complete system consists of a precision Stop-and-Retest Camera, a unique three-axis Storage and Retrieval Unit and an Electrostatic Hardcopy Output Unit.

The Stop-and-Retest Camera was designed to make high resolution microphotographic reproductions of original documents at a 140X reduction ratio, and to precisely locate and store up to 10,000 microimages on a Lippman emulsion film plane.

The three-axis Storage and Retrieval Unit is a high density random access device capable of storing up to one million microphotographic reproductions of documents in less than one cubic foot. The location of each microphotograph is uniquely specified by three binary coded axis designations. Selection of any desired microphotograph is provided by electrical index signals that may be supplied by a digital computer, magnetic tape, punched paper tape, punched cards, or a similar type digital device. Retrieval time averages approximately two seconds per document. Information in the selected microphotograph is transferred from the film plane by optical projection to a Vidicon camera tube.

The principal elements of the Electrostatic Hardcopy Output Unit are the wideband video signal amplifiers, an electrostatic printing tube and the paper handling mechanism. The printing tube forms an image charge pattern on plastic coated paper. This is then developed, resulting in a hardcopy reproduction of the selected original document.

FROM MICROIMAGE TO PRINTOUT—Each of the three little black dots at the left (shown full size) is the reproduction of a microimage of an 8½ x 11" page. Ten thousand such images, at 140x reduction, can be placed on each 10 x 10" memory plane of the prototype microimage library store constructed by Avco Corporation. A module of 100 such memory planes occupies less than a cubic foot and stores one million pages. Any one of these can be found and printed out full size, as in the "hard copy" illustrated above, in approximately two seconds, making use of a Printapix cathode ray tube manufactured by Litton Industries.

by the photostore and placed in focus before the vidicon. The latter scans the image and transmits it to the printing tube. This is a cathode ray tube made by Litton Industries under the name of "Printapix." On the face of this tube is a broken line, 8½ inches long, made up of the ends of thousands of minute conductors, each .001 inch in diameter and spaced .003 inch apart on centers. The signal from the vidicon is converted by the tube to electrical impulses which are transmitted by these conductors and deposited by them as electrostatic charges on a sheet of paper passing in contact with them at a speed of 33 inches a minute. These charges are then developed by methods which have become familiar in connection with the electrostatic copying devices. The resolution of the resultant "hard copy" in consequence approaches the spacing of the conductors, namely, 33 lines per inch. The entire image is read out in one-third of a second. The full cycle of finding the image and producing the "hard copy" is performed in approximately a second.

This result constitutes an impressive engineering achievement. While the "hard copy" still leaves room for improvement with respect to resolution and sharpness, yet the system as a whole is technically capable of sustaining, except for material containing very minute detail, the capabilities of high-ratio reduction which were originally envisioned.

The prospect initially envisioned was that large quantities of research materials might be so compressed photographically that they might be reproduced comparatively cheaply and be stored and serviced by a device such as that which has now been completed. In assessing this prospect against the actual development it appears that although the prototype machine is technically adequate to the purpose (and could easily be improved still further) its prospective high cost (probably in excess of a hundred thousand dollars) would nullify the saving to be derived from the low-cost dissemination for all except very high-rate-of-use situations. Contributing to this conclusion is the fact that the machine is adapted to a high level of rapid and continuous production not likely to be encountered in any except very active installations. Accordingly, while it is expected that the device will find specialized uses, it does not as yet provide the means for widespread exploitation of the capabilities for inexpensive dissemination for library use

offered by high-ratio-reduction photocopying, and further searches for such means remain to be made.

A Reader-Finder for Microfilm Viewing. The location of the desired frame in a roll of microfilm, even after the roll has been affixed to the viewer, is frequently a very tedious operation, involving repeated stopping and searching. Commercial and industrial practice has produced methods of "indexing" the frames in a roll by means of bars or other images printed in varying positions on the film so as to pass along a scale on the viewing screen to indicate a numerical order. Mr. Peter Scott, the head of the Microreproduction Laboratory at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, believes that a superior result can be effected for the book material usually represented in the microfilms used in libraries. For these it should be possible to perceive, without stopping and searching, the usual page numbers or dates (as in the case of newspapers) as finding aids. He has developed the prototype of a device showing how this might be done by using stroboscopic lighting. To explore the validity of his proposal the Council has made a grant to the American Library Association which in turn is making it possible for the Institute to develop Mr. Scott's suggestion in a device for the purpose which might, ideally, be affixed to any microfilm viewer.

Journal Publication in Microform. An earlier report recorded an experiment to ascertain whether the members of a scientific group could effectively employ one of the microforms as a medium of journal publication and what the effects of such publication might be on library practice.⁴¹ In a grant to the American Institute of Biological Sciences the Council, together with the National Science Foundation, made it possible for the Wildlife Disease Association to publish its journal, *Wildlife Disease*, on Microcards. The justification for the experiment was twofold: the members of the association were too few to support a journal in usual form; and their articles, when accepted by other biological journals, were unduly abridged. Publication on Microcards might be within the means of such a small group, yet would not require the emasculation of articles.

The experiment has to this point been ostensibly successful. The membership of the organization has increased from 200

⁴¹ III: 33-34.

to 1,000, an increase which has been attributed to its possession of a journal. The members of the association have agreed to continue the journal for the time being in the present form. Nevertheless, sufficient data to evaluate the experiment properly has not as yet been accumulated; consequently, the National Science Foundation and the Council have extended the grant for an additional year and a half to make it possible to effect a fuller evaluation.

Automatic Book-Cradle/Page-Turner. The inadequacy of available page-turning equipment was found to be one of the limiting factors in connection with the demonstration of closed-circuit television for the consultation of library materials between libraries on the campus of the University of Virginia in 1957-1958.⁴² Other considerations made it seem additionally desirable to develop an adequate device for this purpose. It seemed probable that, if telefacsimile for libraries should become a reality, some more effective device would be needed for exposing books to the transmitter than the awkward arrangement, involving the intermittent manual raising and lowering of a glass pressure-plate, employed in previous experiments of this kind. Also, it seemed desirable to develop such a device for ordinary book-copying. In this work, the book which is being copied is at present forcibly made to lie as nearly flat as possible by the use of a pressure-plate which must be raised and lowered each time a page is turned. This labor constitutes a principal portion of the task of the camera-operator. If this operation could be automated it might be expected that one operator might be able to supervise several cameras at one time.

Accordingly, in 1959 a contract was placed with the de Florez Company for the construction of a working model of an automatic book-cradle/page-turner for microfilm copying. The design of the device contemplated that a book should not be compelled to lie flat, but would be permitted to rest in a cradle at a more comfortable 90° position. This required that the opposing pages would be viewed by the camera in a series of mirrors which would restore the image to flatness on the film. The page-turning mechanism must be sufficiently reliable so as not to foul or tear the pages, must be sensitive enough to detect uncut pages, yet must be able to take care of pages of

⁴² II: 24.

unequal weight, such as inserted plates or the tissues which protect them. The machine should also be able to stop at a predicted point.

The device has been constructed.⁴³ In shop tests it works reliably and rapidly. The questions remain, however, whether it will be reliable in an operating situation, and whether it will enable the camera operator to supervise several cameras at one time. The New York Public Library has agreed to field-test the device in order to answer these questions.

A Scholar's Camera. Ever since the development, four decades ago, of the miniature (35 mm. film) camera, scholars have attempted to employ it or other inexpensive but rapid and faithful copying devices in assembling their notes of research. None of the devices available for the purpose is wholly adequate. The miniature camera ordinarily requires a stand and lighting equipment, while the results of the copying are not known until after later processing of the film. Other devices have been employed. One, which uses an inflated plastic pillow to conform to the contour of the book being copied, can reproduce pages at full scale without the use of a stand. It is portable and has self-contained lighting, but subsequent processing and the accompanying equipment are still required, and the cost of the photosensitive material is about eight cents per exposure.

A device is needed that would be conveniently portable, that would not require subsequent processing but would show results immediately, and for which the per-copy cost would be low. A widely available camera meets the first two of these specifications, but the materials cost of the copies made with its use is approximately twenty-five cents per exposure (one to two pages).

In a preliminary attempt to ascertain what might be effected with available technology, the Council commissioned from the Bell & Howell Company the prototype of a "scholar's camera" intended to produce microfilm with the use of readily available 35 mm. film, to process this film immediately after exposure in a developing tank attached to the camera, and finally to project the film for viewing through the same lens with which it was made. This device was completed during the past year.

⁴³ An illustration of the machine appeared in V: 22.

It does what was asked of it, and the material cost of operating it is approximately four cents per exposure (one to two pages). But it still requires a stand and the procedure which accompanies daylight tank processing. It points the way to further developments.

Photocopying from Bound Volumes. Last year the Library Technology Project commissioned from Mr. William R. Hawken, for many years in charge of the photocopying services at the library of the University of California at Berkeley, an evaluation of the available office-copying devices capable of copying from bound volumes.⁴⁴ The report of this inquiry has been published during the past year and has been favorably received.⁴⁵

Telefacsimile. The Council has continued to support the review, the start of which was reported last year,⁴⁶ of the applicability of telefacsimile to library work. Telefacsimile has been technically feasible for many years, but the conditions under which it is obtained have made it in general unacceptable for library use. Specifically, such systems ordinarily require that the original copy be in single leaves rather than in bound book form; that the transmission either be extremely slow or else that a very expensive broad-band channel (such as a coaxial cable) be employed; and that expensive monitored sending and receiving equipment be employed. However, this is an art which is advancing rapidly, and the Council consequently secured the services of Image Instruments, Inc., of Newton, Massachusetts, to review the available devices and channels with a view to estimating the cost of an adequate library installation at the present time. A report was received early in the year just past.⁴⁷ It indicates that a telefacsimile system between libraries is now technologically and economically feasible, given conditions of need which require much expensive traffic of material between the locations. The Council is now exploring the possibility of a suitable demonstration.

⁴⁴ V: 22.

⁴⁵ William R. Hawken: *Photocopying from Bound Volumes; a Study of Machines, Methods and Materials.* Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, 1962. xvi, 208 p.

⁴⁶ V: 25.

⁴⁷ Facsimile Systems for Improving Library Utility in Large Metropolitan Areas. A Report to the Council on Library Resources, Inc. Newton, Massachusetts: Image Instruments, Inc. . . . Assisted by Intectron Inc., 1961. 7 p.

Meanwhile, however, the art continues to advance rapidly, and the requirements for justification of an installation may be expected to diminish commensurately.

Home Delivery of Books for Public Libraries. In many communities travel distances and parking problems greatly impede the use of library facilities. While in recent years bookmobiles have brought library services to outlying districts in many urban as well as rural areas, no serious attempt has been made in many decades to ascertain whether a community would benefit by home delivery of books ordered by mail or telephone. The Citizens' Library of Washington, Pennsylvania, believed that it would, even though the circulation resulting from its conventional services had tripled in three years. Friends of the library were prepared to meet the cost of advertising lists of available books in the local newspaper, and borrowers would be expected to defray the delivery charges. Additional funds were, however, needed to purchase extra copies of books to meet an anticipated increased demand, to supervise the additional service, and to assemble data wherewith to evaluate the experiment. A small grant has been made for these purposes.

Improvement of the Administrative Bases of Library Work

(Under this head are considered those arrangements which bring the bibliographic apparatus and the books to the service of the inquirer. In this category come library buildings and the other physical apparatus and mechanisms associated with the custody of the books, the presentation of bibliographical information and the service to readers. Here come also the matters relating to the government and inter-institutional relations of the library, recruitment of staff, fiscal arrangements, systems of record-keeping, standardizing and testing, the arrangements by which inter-library cooperation is effected, and overall planning for improvement.)

Mechanization in Libraries. A number of the projects described in this report have dealt with the development of mechanisms for specific library applications. In addition to

these, the Council has supported three general inquiries to ascertain the possible role of the advanced data processing mechanisms (typified by the computers) in library work. One of these, the investigation of concepts and problems of libraries of the future, is described in earlier pages. A second, an inquiry into the possible applications of computer-based procedures in large research libraries has progressed during the year at the Library of Congress.⁴⁸ A third was completed during the year just past.

In 1960 the Council made a grant to enable the Library of the Chicago Undergraduate Division of the University of Illinois to investigate the application of advanced data processing techniques to the procedures of a university library, with especial relationship to its own prospective rapid growth in terms of size of collections and number of persons served. The investigation was executed by a team of staff members of the Chicago Division Library, of which Mr. Edward M. Heiliger is Librarian, working with a team from the General Electric Company. The results of the study have been published.⁴⁹

The writers of the report believe that significant improvement of services in a situation such as was studied can best be effected with the assistance of computers, and they propose a number of new services, to be provided with such assistance. These include: the production of daily listings of books on order, received, in process and cataloged; a weekly listing of periodicals received and an annual listing of complete periodical holdings; a listing of holdings arranged by subject headings; and a daily listing of books in circulation. The report provides flow-charts and cost analyses, and presents a series of recommendations for immediate next steps. It suggests, among other things, that the present catalog of 60,000 titles be converted to machine-readable form in the next two years.

In another instance of attempts to apply automata to bibliographical and library work, in April 1962 the Secretary of Agriculture inaugurated a study of the possibility of such applications to the provision of scientific information to workers in agricultural research not only in the Department of

⁴⁸ V: 29.

⁴⁹ Louis A. Schultheiss, Don S. Culbertson, and Edward M. Heiliger: *Advanced Data Processing in the University Library*. New York, The Scarecrow Press, 1962. xiv, 388 p.

Agriculture but throughout the country, including experiment stations and land-grant institutions. The Council has made it possible for one of the latter (the University of Florida) to assign a member of its library staff to the study for a period.

Standardization in Library Work. The American Standards Association has long maintained a sectional committee devoted especially to the bibliographical aspects of library work and documentation in which representatives of various interests join to develop standards such as those affecting citation, indexing, layout of periodicals, abbreviations, and transliteration. The committee is the American counterpart of one in the International Standards Organization which has similar affiliations with other national committees. For want of a secretariat the work of the American committee has suffered and it has not been able to support effectively its share of the work at the international level. During the past year the Council, matching a similar grant by the National Science Foundation, made a grant to the New York Public Library to assist the committee with secretariat services.

The Library Technology Project. In considering the means whereby technical improvements in library operations might be developed and brought to attention, the need early became evident for the establishment of an organization concerned with the gathering and dissemination of information of this kind, with the standardization and testing of library equipment and supplies, and with the development of improved devices and services. It seemed desirable, also, that such a group should work in close contact with the libraries which it would serve. Consequently, after an initial survey, a grant was made to the American Library Association to establish the Library Technology Project to undertake these tasks. This office came into being in May 1959,⁵⁰ and has now completed its third year. Its activities are reflected in annual reports and in special publications reporting the results of testing, standardization and development.

As continuing activities the Project publishes a monthly bulletin of information in the *ALA Bulletin* and in *Special Libraries* (the journal of the Special Libraries Association, which is represented on the Project's advisory board); it

⁵⁰ III: 39; IV: 20; V: 27-28.

sponsors a sectional committee of the American Standards Association for the development of standards and specifications for library supplies and equipment; it provides a reference service to libraries by mail and telephone on supplies and equipment and distributes compilations of purchasing information to them; it presents exhibits of devices and sources of information at library conferences, and has organized and conducted a library equipment institute.

The Project has undertaken testing, standardizing and other evaluative studies directed at the following:

- Adhesives (published*)
- Mylar laminating equipment (published)
- Systems of circulation control (published)
- Ink for marking manuscripts (reported)
- Equipment for photocopying from bound volumes
(published; see page 31)
- Catalog card stock (published; see page 20;
Phase II, in progress)
- Bookbinding (Phase I, published, see page 22;
Phase II, in progress)
- Library-type record players (published)
- Equipment for reproducing catalog cards (in
preparation for publication)

* The following publications, in addition to those listed elsewhere in this report, appeared during the past fiscal year:

Library Technology. Evaluation of GBC Laminator. *ALA Bulletin*, 56: 56-57. January 1962.

— Manuscript-marking Ink Being Tested. *ALA Bulletin*, 56: 264. March 1962; and: Manuscript-marking Ink. *ALA Bulletin*, 56: 361. April 1962.

The Testing and Evaluation of Record Players for Libraries: a Report based on a Study conducted for the Library Technology Project by Consumers' Research, Inc. Chicago: Library Technology Project, American Library Association, [1962]. viii, 76 p.

Study of Circulation Control Systems, Public Libraries, College and University Libraries, Special Libraries, by George Fry & Associates, Inc. (Chicago, 1961, 138 p.), was listed in the previous annual report: p. 53, item 121.

Since the close of the fiscal year the following has appeared: Gladys T. Piez. Some Library Adhesives—A Laboratory Evaluation of P.V.A.'s. *ALA Bulletin*, 56: 838-843. October 1962.

Pressure-sensitive tapes (completed; not published)

Protective coatings for microfilm (in progress)

Equipment for producing full-scale copies from microcopies (in progress)

Wood library furniture (in progress)

It has initiated a number of projects for the development of improved devices:

Pamphlet box (completed; ready for exploitation)

Newspaper stick (in progress)

Adhesive for labeling books (in progress)

Equipment for testing wood library furniture (in progress)

Archival container (in progress)

Container for shipping books (in progress)

Microfilm finder-reader (in progress)

Card-holding device for typewriters (unsuccessful)

Its projects for the improvement of systems or services have included the following:

Fire (and other hazards) insurance policy (completed; in preparation for publication)

Book charging system for small libraries (completed; in preparation for publication)

Use of permanent/durable book paper (in progress)

The Project is thus fully justifying the expectation made of it, and is being continued.

Standards of Archival Administration. While the arrangements for record preservation and service made by the National Archives and a number of the state archival agencies are admirable, there are too many in which such arrangements are inadequate. The problem of securing the general adoption of adequate standards is of course one of general public importance, but is of especial concern to users of historical records, and is one of the objectives of the Society of American Archivists. The Society has reached the conclusion that a

survey which would display the actual facts of archival administration at the state level is needed at the present time to promote the general adoption of adequate standards. The Council has made a grant to the Society to make such a survey possible. It is being conducted by Dr. Ernst Posner, well-known for his contributions to archival science in this country and in Europe. It is planned that the report of the survey will be so published and disseminated with the aid of interested collaborating groups as to make it most likely to be productive of practical results.

Reimbursement of Costs of Library Services in Support of Research Contracts. A very real problem to many research libraries has derived from the extent to which their services have been burdened by demands arising from the execution of Government and other research contracts undertaken by the institutions of which they are a part. These contracts have typically assumed additional services by the library but have made inadequate provision to enable the library to furnish them. Two years ago the Council made a small grant to the Association of Research Libraries to seek solutions to this problem.⁵¹ A report of this inquiry has been published.⁵² From other information also it is known that the search met with a considerable measure of success.

Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges. With assistance from the Rockefeller Brothers Fund the seven liberal arts colleges comprising this Foundation have over the past six years developed a "cooperative library system" involving division of responsibility for acquisition and sharing of collections, and during the period have added 18,000 volumes to the common stock. The group now seeks to widen the basis and to increase the usefulness of the system through the exchange of cataloging information, the preparation of a union list of serials, the development of a cooperative library of audio-visual materials, and in other ways. One of these involves an evaluation of the cooperative acquisitions program with a view to weighing the desirability of changing present acquisitions assignments and of adding others, the evaluation of periodical holdings, and other measures. The Council has

⁵¹ IV: 21.

⁵² Richard H. Logsdon: Indirect Costs of Library Services under U. S. Research Agreement. *College & Research Libraries* 21: 24-27 (January 1962).

1.

INTER-LIBRARY COOPERATION

— In Colorado seven academic libraries are investigating the feasibility of a cooperative technical processing program and of sharing collections by a special courier system. The libraries are: 1., Colorado State College, Greeley; 2., University of Colorado, Boulder; 3., Colorado State University, Fort Collins; 4., Colorado School of Mines, Golden; 5., Western State College, Gunnison; 6., Fort Lewis Agricultural and Mechanical College, Durango; 7., Adams State College, Alamosa.

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made it possible for the Foundation to secure the services of an expert to make such a survey, the report of which, it is expected, will be published.

Library Resources in Canada. In a report prepared for the National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges, its Library Survey Committee concluded that the sciences are being reasonably well served by the libraries of the country, but that collections in the humanities and social sciences are relatively weak to the point that research and training in research are hampered. The Committee recommended that a survey be made of the principal libraries to ascertain which collections were strongest in certain areas, and that a plan for institutional specialization be developed. At the request of the Committee, of which Dr. W. Kaye Lamb, the National Librarian of Canada, is chairman, the Council has made a grant to permit the employment of an outside expert, Mr. Edwin E. Williams, Counselor on Collections, Harvard University Library, and long involved in the cooperative acquisitions arrangements developed under the Farmington Plan, to conduct the survey and to make recommendations. After visits to fourteen of the major libraries, Mr. Williams is now preparing a report for publication.

Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado. A grant has been made to this Association to explore methods for the more effective sharing of resources both of books and of manpower. Two possibilities are being explored: establishing a cooperative technical processing program, and transmission of interlibrary loans directly from one academic library to another within the state by a special courier. Should the experiment prove successful, it may very possibly offer an example which can be useful elsewhere.

Bibliographical Center for Research, Rocky Mountain Region (Denver). For more than twenty years this Center has provided a notable example of regional interlibrary cooperation, providing union catalog and bibliographic clearing-house services for more than two hundred libraries in an area extending over eleven states. During the past year the Council through a small grant enabled Mr. John W. Cronin, Director of the Processing Department of the Library of Congress, to consult with the officers of the Center to relate regional activities more closely to national plans.

Lorain County (Ohio) Public Library Organization. A grant has been made to this Organization, of which Mr. Merlin D. Wolcott is chairman, for a survey of public library service in the county with a view to planning future development. The situation in the county has familiar features: in an area of 495 square miles having a population of 217,500 there are seven autonomous libraries, yet these do not completely serve the area. The question to be explored is whether a plan of organization and support can be devised which will provide for better use — in terms of service rendered — of the available funds and which will be convincing to the jurisdictions which now have libraries. This is a question of state-wide — and indeed of much wider — relevance. The survey, which has been commenced by Miss Mildred Sandoe and Mr. E. Paul Beckerman, is consequently being executed in discussion with the State Librarian, Mr. Walter Brahm.

School Libraries in Puerto Rico. In an area somewhat larger than that of Delaware, Puerto Rico supports a population more than five times as large — larger than that of 24 of the states. The responsibility of education for the future of Puerto Rico is enormous, and — within the educational system — the contribution of school libraries may prove an important determinant. Professor Mary V. Gaver has been in the forefront of those who have attempted to realize the potential contribution which school libraries can make to instruction and education. Last year she was invited by the Puerto Rican Ministry of Education to survey the school libraries of the Commonwealth in cooperation with the Sociedad de Bibliotecarios de Puerto Rico with view to estimating actual and future needs. A small grant has made this possible.

Libraries in Underdeveloped Areas. The International Relations Office of the American Library Association was established in 1956 with the aid of a three-year grant from the Rockefeller Foundation. A second grant for a four-year period provides for a director, some secretarial assistance and travel expenses. Believing that the activities of this Office constitute effective means for furnishing assistance to libraries overseas and especially in underdeveloped countries, the Council has supplemented the Rockefeller funds to provide for an assistant director and other expenses.

Books for Neo-Literates in Latin America. The “Books for

the People" Fund (*Fondo "El Libro del Pueblo"*) has been established in the belief that victory in the war on illiteracy in Latin America requires not only learning how to read but the easy availability of books worth reading once reading skills have been acquired. The Fund, a non-profit organization with headquarters in the Pan American Union, plans to select books for translation into Spanish and Portuguese, as well as to use the works of Latin American authors, and to utilize mass production and distribution techniques, including the establishment of school libraries, in collaboration with national ministries of education. The Council has made a small grant to assist the Fund to develop a plan of action.

Population Trends and Libraries. Changing age groups and the migrations of the country's population have their implications for planning future library service. The Council therefore, as previously reported,⁵³ made a small grant to the University of Illinois, whose Graduate School of Library Science publishes *Library Trends*, for an article analyzing data from the 1960 Census for publication in the periodical. The analysis was made by Philip M. Hauser, Director of the Population Research and Training Center, University of Chicago, and Martin Taitel, Statistician at the Center, and has been published.⁵⁴

The Farmington Plan. The program for the cooperative acquisition of foreign publications, known as the "Farmington Plan," in which a large group of research libraries participate, has been described in the past.⁵⁵ With aid from the Council, the program has been reviewed and in view of its usefulness plans have been made for extending the areas of activity. The increase in activities has required preparation of a revised handbook, which has been published.⁵⁶

⁵³ IV: 21.

⁵⁴ Philip M. Hauser and Martin Taitel: Population Trends—Prologue to Library Development. *Library Trends*, 10: 10-67. July 1961.

⁵⁵ III: 30-31.

⁵⁶ Edwin E. Williams: *Farmington Plan Handbook, Revised to 1961 and Abridged*. [Office of the Executive Secretary, Association of Research Libraries, Cornell University Library, Ithaca, New York, 1961.] 140 p.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Accountant's Opinion

August 20, 1962

To the Board of Directors of

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements present fairly the assets, liabilities and the fund balance of the Council on Library Resources Inc. at June 30, 1962 and the expenditures and income for the year then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

June 30, 1962

ASSETS

Cash		\$ 107,697
Investments		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximate market):		
due July 12, 1962	\$ 99,884	
due July 15, 1962	499,412	
due August 16, 1962	99,627	
Savings account, including \$15,404 accrued interest	515,404	1,214,327
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation		7,000,000
Deposits		516
		\$8,322,540

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable, per accompanying statement		\$ 715,488
Accounts payable		5,649
Fund balance		
Balance June 30, 1961	\$ 643,900	
Add — Grant from The Ford Foundation (Note)	8,000,000	
	8,643,900	
Deduct — Expenditures less income for the year, per accompanying statement	1,042,497	
Balance June 30, 1962 (of which \$683,706 has been appropriated for certain grants and contracts)		7,601,403
		\$8,322,540

NOTE

The Ford Foundation approved an additional grant of \$8,000,000 effective July 1, 1961 to the Council on Library Resources, Inc. in order that the Council may continue for a seven-to-ten year period its programs of research and demonstration in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular.

STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

For the Year Ended June 30, 1962

EXPENDITURES

Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects, per accompanying statement	\$961,128	
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded, per accompanying statement	<u>35,073</u>	
		\$ 926,055

General administrative expense

Compensation and employee benefits	119,609	
Rent	7,200	
Professional services	3,055	
Travel and meetings	12,614	
Furniture and equipment	102	
Supplies, printing, insurance, communications and other	<u>14,620</u>	157,200
		<u>\$1,083,255</u>

INCOME

From investments		<u>40,758</u>
Expenditures less income		<u><u>\$1,042,497</u></u>

STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1962

	Payable June 30, 1961	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1962
American Association of Law Libraries Advisory committee on Project Lawsearch.....		\$ 2,500		\$ 2,500	
American Historical Association Compilation of a Guide to Photocopied Historical Materials in the United States and Canada..			\$ 3,383	(3,383)	
American Institute of Biological Sciences Continuation of experimental publication of a scientific journal in microform		8,724			\$ 8,724
American Library Association Implementation of the 1960 School Library Standards	\$ 75,000			75,000	
Library resources fact finding survey.....			3,018	(3,018)	
Library Technology Project Development of a microfilm reader-finder system		27,070		27,070	
Development of improved board for archival containers		25,194		25,194	
Development of performance standards for library bookbinding—Phase II		42,890		21,445	21,445
Extension of Library Technology Project to June 30, 1962	172,577	111,419		283,952	44
Projects of testing and standardization.....	24,548		17,512	7,036	
Publication and implementation of report of the study of circulation control	21,802	9,515		31,317	
Planning a "Library of the Future" exhibit for the Century 21 Exposition, Seattle, 1962....	5,991	1,493		7,484	
Publication of a book-selection service at the college library level		150,000			150,000
Study of the feasibility of developing a numerical code for identifying current American publications			753	(753)	
Support of the ALA International Relations Office		89,645		17,929	71,716
Support of the work of the ALA Committee on a Permanent/Durable Paper		13,184		13,184	
Travel grant to promote international co-ordination of cataloging rules		675		675	
American Library Association (co-sponsor with Association of Research Libraries) Preparation of a book on the planning of college/university library buildings	35,365				35,365
Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges Re-evaluation of the co-operative library system of the Arkansas Foundation of Associated Colleges		5,130			5,130

	Payable June 30, 1961	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1962
Association of Citizens Library of Washington (Pennsylvania) Experiment in public library home delivery of books		\$10,000		\$10,000	
Association of Research Libraries Study of statistical basis for planning the preservation of research library material....		1,590	\$90	1,500	
Extension of the Farmington Plan for the Co- operative Acquisition of Foreign Publications..			1,123	(1,123)	
Study of bibliographical control of microforms..			1,647	(1,647)	
Association of State Institutions of Higher Education in Colorado Study of feasibility of a co-operative technical processing program		5,000		5,000	
Avco Corporation Addition of hard copy output to the high- density photographic store	\$58,847			58,847	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relating to preservation of books and other library materials		125,100		64,097	\$61,003
Battelle Memorial Institute Investigations looking to improved viewing of microimages	16,400	81		16,481	
Bell & Howell Company Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	154,603			47,612	106,991
Fabrication of prototype of a scholar's camera..	9,687			9,687	
Bibliographic Center for Research (Denver) For procurement of consultative services		500	235	265	
Bolt Beranek and Newman, Inc. Research on concepts and problems of libraries of the future		162,258		47,575	114,683
Books for the People Fund, Inc. Children's books for Latin America— feasibility study		5,000		5,000	
Brookings Institution Survey of Federal libraries		2,250		2,250	
Brown University A study in support of university-school- community library co-ordination	12,000			12,000	
Church, Randolph W. Inquiry to develop a plan of investigation of the life expectancy of books in American libraries		300		300	
Committee on Bibliography, Seminar on the Acquisition of Latin American Library Materials Exploration of feasibility of a Caribbean bibliographic center		600	104	496	

	Payable June 30, 1961	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1962
The de Florez Company, Inc.					
Field test of automatic book-cradle/page-turner.		\$1,000			\$1,000
Working model of an automatic book-cradle/ page-turner	\$2,647			\$1,902	745
Working model of a book-copying cradle/press. .	6,500			5,818	682
Working model of a catalog card duplicator. . . .	5,975			4,519	1,456
Development of a continuing book-selection service for college libraries*	900		\$792	108	
Emory University					
Grant in aid of a new edition of The Adminis- tration of the College Library by Guy R. Lyle.			28	(28)	
Expenses connected with the study of concepts and problems of libraries of the future*		5,000		3,121	1,879
Forbes & Waite					
Preliminary investigation of physical/economic factors involved in miniaturizing research library collections	2,500			2,500	
George Fry & Associates					
Study of book-circulation systems	755		755		
Mary V. Gaver (Graduate School of Library Service, Rutgers)					
Survey of school library facilities in Puerto Rico		5,000		5,000	
Image Instruments, Inc.					
Investigation of the applicability of electronic systems to library service in metropolitan areas	2,185	878	14	3,049	
Intectron Incorporated					
Investigation of factors affecting high-reduction microphotography	22,691			20,958	1,733
International Association of Music Libraries (on behalf of the International Joint Commission on the International Inventory of Music Sources)					
For support of work on the Inventory		10,000		10,000	
International Federation of Library Associations					
An international conference on the principles of cataloging, 1961	75,420			75,420	
Jonker Business Machines, Inc.					
Development of equipment for an inexpensive disseminable mechanical system for searching legal literature	37,730			37,730	
Library of Congress					
Assistance toward the development of a shelf- classification for law books			10	(10)	
Creation of a national union catalog of manuscript collections (supplement)		10,000		10,000	
Development of Library of Congress classifica- tion for Anglo-American Law		34,200		17,100	17,100

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1961	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1962
Meeting to plan photocopying of European manuscript sources for American history....			\$660	(\$600)	
Study of possibilities of mechanization in large research libraries	\$70,000			50,000	\$20,000
Lorain County Public Library Organization A survey of the public libraries of Lorain County, Ohio		\$8,000		8,000	
Massachusetts Institute of Technology Feasibility study of the design of an automatic catalog card replicator	14,238			14,238	
Meeting on preparation of a nation-wide plan for metropolitan library service*	432		301	131	
John R. Miles Company Development of a microscope-magnifier for reading micro-opaques	622	8,262		8,884	
Music Library Association To record the holdings of American libraries for inclusion in the International Inventory of Musical Sources		13,200		13,200	
National Bureau of Standards State-of-the-art review of mechanized information selection and facsimile retrieval systems			4,350	(4,350)	
National Conference of Canadian Universities and Colleges Survey of collections in the humanities and social sciences in Canadian university libraries		4,750		4,750	
New York Public Library Field test of automatic book-cradle/page-turner		7,250		7,250	
New York Public Library (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39 on Library Work and Documentation) Development of standards in library work and documentation		8,470		8,470	
Planning for the stabilization of the storage needs of libraries through photocopying — miscellaneous expenses*		1,000	263	737	
Project Lawsearch (The Michie Company, Matthew Bender & Company, Inc. and The Bureau of National Affairs, Inc.) Development of a disseminable, mechanical information search system for legal literature	29,000			24,000	5,000
Purdue Research Foundation (on behalf of Thermophysical Properties Research Center) Publication and dissemination of Masters Theses in the Pure and Applied Sciences, Vol. 4			35	(35)	

* Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1961	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (refunds)	Payable June 30, 1962
Society of American Archivists					
A study of state archives		\$42,000		\$28,000	\$14,000
Thompson Ramo Wooldridge, Inc.					
Studies in word correlation and automatic indexing, Phases I and IIA	\$47,347			24,598	22,749
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Florida					
Participation by University of Florida in Task Force ABLE (Agricultural, Biological Literature Exploitation)		2,000		2,000	
University of Pittsburgh					
Searching statutory law by computer	29,443				29,443
Yale University					
Development and demonstration of the basis, operation and results of the Yale University Library's selective book retirement program ..	50,000			50,000	
	<u>\$1,009,805</u>	<u>\$961,128</u>	<u>\$35,073</u>	<u>\$1,220,372</u>	<u>\$715,488</u>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the title-page, is reproduced from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The picture has been reproduced in previous annual reports of the Council.

The Chinese version of the picture, which appears on the front cover and on the title-page, is taken from a copy, in the Library of Congress, of the *Ku chin tu shu chi ch'eng*, edition of 1895-1898. This is a reprint of an eighteenth century work which took the picture from the *Yüan hsi ch'i t'u shuo*. This last mentioned work was a collaboration by Father Jean Terrenz, S.J., (1576-1630), and a Chinese scholar, Wang Cheng.

The characters above the picture can be translated, "Book Rack Diagram." The characters in the vertical column at the side give, at the top, the general title of the work ("Complete collection of extracts from ancient and modern works, illustrated"), and then other information ("Section on administration, sub-section on handicrafts, chapter 249: section on 'remarkable machines,' sub-section 'Collection of extracts,' leaf no. 57").

Herbert A. Giles in his essay, "The Mariner's Compass," reproduced the picture and called attention to the fact that the book-wheel was of Western origin as indicated by "bound books in the bookcase, standing on end instead of lying, Chinese fashion, on their sides." (*Adversaria Sinica*. Shanghai: 1914. p. 108.) This wheel, which has a horizontal axis, and others revolving on a vertical axis are discussed in L. Carrington Goodrich's essay, "The Revolving Book-Case in China." (*Harvard Journal of Asiatic Studies*, 7: July 1942. p. 130-161.)

Thanks are due Professor Schuyler V. R. Cammann, of the University of Pennsylvania, and Dr. Edwin G. Beal, Jr., Head of the Chinese Section, Library of Congress, and his colleague, Dr. K. T. Wu, for their aid in locating the picture and providing information.

A number of ex-libris from North American academic and other research libraries were reproduced as decorative material in the Council's fifth annual report. Because this aroused considerable interest, a random selection of ex-libris and book-stamps from abroad are reproduced this year. Thanks are due the directors of these cooperating institutions, whose book-marks are identified by number. (It should be noted that many of these book-marks have had to be reduced in size.) The book-marks are:

1. Koninklijke Bibliotheek, The Hague. Book-plate used for gifts of the Society of Friends of the Royal Library of the Netherlands.
2. Trinity College, Dublin. Book-plate designed by Michael O'Connor and printed by the Dolmen Press, Dublin, for use in a campaign for contributions to the Irish library's extension fund.
3. University of Cape Town Libraries, Cape Town. One of the chief book-plates used by the South African university.
4. Adayar Library and Research Centre, Madras, India.
5. British Museum, London. Rubbing of commonly used binding stamp.
6. State M. E. Saltykov-Schedrin Public Library, Leningrad. Publishing mark, or imprint, used by the Russian library.
7. Landsbókasafn Islands, Reykjavik.
8. Real Biblioteca de San Lorenzo de El Escorial, El Escorial. One of several book-stamps used by the Spanish library.
9. Biblioteka Jagiellonska, Cracow. Ex-libris of a type which has been in use at this Polish library since the sixteenth century.
10. National Library, Athens.
11. Bibliothèque de l'Institut Boudhique, Phnom-Penh, Cambodia.
12. University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong.
13. Bibliothèque Nationale, Luxembourg.
14. Bodleian Library, Oxford.
15. Biblioteca Ambrosiana, Milan.
16. Auckland Public Library, Auckland. Ex-libris, incorporating the coat-of-arms of the New Zealand city, for a special collection.
17. Bibliothèque Nationale, Phnom-Penh, Cambodia.
18. Kungl. Biblioteket, Stockholm. The Swedish Royal Library uses this ex-libris on paper of several different colors.
19. Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Vatican City State.
20. National Library of Australia, Canberra. Ex-libris used for a special collection, that of Sir John Ferguson, author of *Bibliography of Australia, 1784-1850*.
21. National Taiwan University, Taipei. The three book-stamps are used on the title-page, page one, and certain other pages, respectively.
22. National Diet Library, Tokyo.
23. Bibliothèque Nationale Suisse-Schweizerische Landesbibliothek, Berne. The design of this ex-libris was chosen in 1933 following a competition open to Swiss artists.
24. Cambridge University. Stamp used on incoming English books.
25. Madras Government Oriental Manuscripts Library, India.
26. Országos Széchényi Könyvtár, Budapest. Woodcut ex-libris of about 1775 with the coat-of-arms of Count Ferenc Széchényi, founder of the National Library.
27. Jewish National and University Library, Jerusalem. The space in the center of the book-plate is usually filled in with the name of a special collection or of a donor, in Hebrew and English.
28. Bibliothèque Générale et Archives, Rabat, Morocco.
29. Royal University of Malta, Valletta.
30. Arquivo Nacional da Torre do Tombo, Lisbon.
31. Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale Vittorio Emanuele, Rome.
32. Biblioteca Nacional, Lisbon.
- 33-34. Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique, Brussels.
35. Korea University Library, Seoul.
36. Silliman University, Dumaguete City, Republic of the Philippines.
37. Dag Hammarskjöld Library, United Nations, New York City. Legend from a book pocket. An ex-libris is being designed.
38. National Library of Scotland, Edinburgh.
39. Narodna Biblioteka — Centralna za Narodnu Republiku Srbiju, Belgrade.
40. University College of the West Indies, Mona, St. Andrew, Jamaica.
41. Archivo General de Indias, Seville.
42. Universitetsbiblioteket, Oslo. The principal ex-libris used by the Royal University Library in large book donations.
43. Bibliothèque Nationale, Paris.
44. American University of Beirut, Lebanon.

22

23

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33

34

35

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37

36

38

39

40

41

42

43

44

圖架書

Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-
1956/57-
Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

020.624

58-915 rev

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